

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Project Number: 823782

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 40 months

Report on **Milestone 30**

Recommendations for a platform for further expansion

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Milestone	30/04/22 (M40)
Actual Achievement Date	13/04/22
Lead Beneficiary/LTP	CESSDA ERIC / GESIS
Work Package	WP5 Innovations in Data Access
Task	Task 5.4 Remote Access to Sensitive Data
Version	V 1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.5

Abstract:

The purpose of this milestone is to highlight one section of the Deliverable D5.10 White Paper on Remote Access to Sensitive Data in the Social Sciences and Humanities: 2021 and Beyond. This section concerns recommendations for proposed future solutions.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020); H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, under the agreement No. 823782

Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
GESIS	Elizabeth Bishop	ElizabethLea.Bishop@gesis.org

1. Introduction

Within Work Package 5 of SSHOC, subtask 5.4 was focused on the need to improve remote access to sensitive data in the social sciences and humanities. The outputs have, broadly, fallen into two groups: 1) practical tools and resources for achieving this objective, and 2) a white paper that offers context, assessment of selected existing solutions, and recommendations for future initiatives. The tools and resources are likely to have an impact in the near future, whereas the white paper and its recommendations will, ideally, contribute to longer term planning in this domain.

2. Description of the Milestone

2.1. Role of the Milestone

The purpose of this milestone is to highlight one section of the Deliverable D5.10 White Paper on Remote Access to Sensitive Data in the Social Sciences and Humanities: 2021 and Beyond. This section concerns recommendations for proposed future solutions.

2.2. Means of verification

This Milestone can be verified by consulting the final version of the [White Paper](#). The text of the recommendations is also provided in Appendix 1.

2.3. Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

While early delivery would have had benefits, this milestone was completed on time. Other deliverables in our task were delayed for technical and legal reasons, and this in turn delayed the completion of the White Paper. It was also felt that getting substantial external input for the recommendations was essential. In addition to the formal external peer review, a number of informal consultations were also made, including with directors of other platforms providing remote access to sensitive data. These inputs substantially improved the final recommendations.

3. Conclusions and next steps

At the conclusion of the SSHOC project, there is as yet no formal structure for continuing the work of SSHOC. That said, work is in progress on Memoranda of Understanding and it is to be hoped that this structure will become formalised. In the meantime, for one of the recommendations, some “bridging” activity has been agreed. The UK Data Service and GESIS will contribute resources toward sustaining some activities of the newly established International Secure Data Facility Professionals Network (ISDFPN) (Deliverable 5.12). This activity directly supports one of the recommendations in Section (2) below: *Networking the (human) community of secure data access professionals*

4. Recommendations

These recommendations are guided by our observations that most successful infrastructures embody two features: 1) they are human as well as technical, and 2) they are neither purely centralised nor decentralised, but well-crafted hybrids.

Infrastructures must, of course, provide essential “plumbing” - hardware, software, platforms, resources, and so on. However, without adequate human support (FTEs, skills, training, etc.), too often infrastructures are built but not adopted, embraced but not established, or started but not sustained. And by nature of their specialist niche, secure data professionals tend to be widely distributed, sometimes only a single individual within a large institution. Improving human networks is essential.

Similarly, for those more familiar with high-powered computing facilities, small-scale growth can appear messy, even chaotic. It can be tempting to believe that the solution is to select “best practice”, centralise, standardise and roll-out. We believe a hybrid-model combining centralised and decentralised elements, is most likely to succeed in the SSH context. Some centralised elements are essential, especially regarding coordination and sustainability. However, flexibility is equally necessary to address not only diversity between social sciences and humanities, but also within each domain (e.g., FORS must address sensitive data from a wide range of disciplines when establishing its service).

Appendix

Recommendations

- 1) Explore and assess if the idea of “Remote Access to Sensitive Data as a Service” as a Service Hub within EOSC is viable. At least two areas of work seem amenable to being supported in this manner.
 - Better provisioning of legal opinions and services needed to establish remote access.

A robust finding of this task has been the complexity of finding legal solutions for accessing sensitive data. Whether for bilateral agreements to connect safe enclaves in two countries or scaling up within a single country, creating legal frameworks is laborious. Once solutions are developed, effective dissemination to others within the same legal system could expedite development for others. This work should build on the strong foundation established in Work Package 8 of SSHOC¹.

One central obstacle often involves the prohibition of certain data from leaving the country and consequently the obligation to leave them on national servers. This is a point on which it should be possible to change laws and practices, at least within the EU. Cross-boundary access has been negotiated, for example by IAB, CASD, and most recently between GESIS and UKDS, but a more generic legal solution would greatly ease the process for future data access.

- IT services hub and perhaps a “basic” certified provider.

The situation is not dissimilar regarding IT. Solutions are now available (e.g., CASD), but finding, assessing, and determining what works with existing local infrastructures remain major challenges. A central hub offering IT consulting could be a solution. Factors to consider include: certification for a designated provider and certification criteria for organisations choosing to implement customised solutions. There is also the matter of costs: where services are provided through data archives, they have typically been free to the user. However, the sustainability of this model needs to be reviewed. Where solutions can be found that work for both social sciences and humanities, these are especially worthy of support.

- 2) Expansion through Networking of Networks

- Recent years have seen substantial growth, albeit fitful and at times fragmented. Safe rooms are being added (FORS) and facilities that already had operational safe rooms are adding remote desktop access. From there, growth often takes the form of connecting hubs, such as with the established IDAN network, and the recently launched RDCnet, which is connecting data centres

¹ Hansen et al. 2022

throughout Germany. The recommendation is to support this type of growth, and make it more efficient (e.g., templates for legal documents, IT advice, coordinating expert advice. In short, to stop reinventing the same wheel. Even if legal barriers prevent extensive cross-border access for the time-being, the vision is still worthy. Moreover, even when data itself cannot be made accessible, much know-how and development ideas can still be profitably exchanged.

- Networking the (human) community of secure data access professionals

The demand for access to sensitive data, in ever more convenient modes, is growing and this growth will continue. A central challenge is to provide the community of experts committed to meeting this demand with resources and institutional support to deliver. Subtask 5.4 within the SSHOC project has successfully established just such an international community. While two national groups (e.g., in the UK and in Germany) are currently viable, a sustainable model should be found for this new international network. Also the continuation of the collaboration started with the SSHOC project offers the prospect of establishing a knowledge hub to keep providing expertise with respect to RSA set-up and operation.